

INCREASING YOUTH KNOWLEDGE IN HANDLING SYNCOPE CASES IN STUDENTS OF THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL OF MUHAMMADIYAH 3 SIDOARJO, TULANGAN SUB-DISTRICT, SIDOARJO DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

First Aid Health Promotion Activities in syncope cases at the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District is a form of education in the form of counseling aimed at increasing adolescent knowledge about first aid methods when encountering syncope cases. The activity was held on November 15, 2018 at the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District. With the goal is students of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District. Before the implementation of the activity, there is a process of preparing activities for 3 weeks before the activities are carried out, starting from the selection of health counseling materials to the submission of permits to related parties. As an evaluation, the activity was attended by 35 students and 1 teacher as participants participating in the activity with enthusiasm and conduciveness, activities can be carried out on time smoothly.

Keywords: Syncope, first aid health promotion, adolescent's knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

According to Hidayat (2006), syncope is a condition of sudden loss of consciousness, and is usually temporary, caused by a lack of blood flow and oxygen to the brain. The first symptom a person

feels before syncope is feeling dizzy, reduced vision, tinnitus, and a burning sensation. Furthermore, the person's vision will darken and he will fall.

Syncope can be a reaction to pain and fear, or because it is very angry, very tired

and lacking in food but more often because physical activity has long been reduced. Blood also builds up in the lower part of the body so that only a small amount reaches the brain.

Characteristics of syncope: pale, cold sweat, lack of response when talking, dizzy eyes, ringing in the ears, a little dizzy. One factor is not eating, overheating, cold, drop conditions (Ramadhan, 2008).

Data on the number of syncope events in adolescents provide a significant incidence of around 5-10% per year. The cause of syncope or fainting is the condition of not eating, heat experienced by children to adolescents.

It is very important for health workers to provide counseling to adolescents. Therefore, we conducted counseling on how to handle first if we found syncope, whether it was in the school area or outside the school.

OBJECTIVES

General Purpose

After taking health promotion, the students of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District can understand first aid in people who have syncope.

Special Purpose

After taking health promotion measures, it is expected that the students of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District can:

1. Understand the meaning of syncope.
2. Mention the causes of syncope.
3. Mention the signs and symptoms of syncope
4. Recite the procedure for first aid in people with syncope

PLAN OF ACTION

Strategy Plan

The strategy plan implemented, including:

1. Coordinate with the principal of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District to apply for permission to carry out health education or counseling as an activity of the nursing program and to help provide guidance to the students of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District.
2. Establish students in the implementation of health education or counseling to know about how to handle syncope cases.
3. Contract time with the students of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District.
4. Provide health promotion about how to handle syncope cases.

Implementation

Actions taken in the implementation of these activities, including:

1. Contacted the principal of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District to request permission for activities and gather the students of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District.
2. Prepare a place and counseling media.
3. The students of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District received extension materials.

Setting

This activity was carried out at the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District.

Target

Target in this activity is all of students at the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The activity was carried out on Thursday, November 15, 2018 at 10:00 WIB at the XI classroom of SMA 3 Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo. The participants were 35 children and 1 teacher. Participants seemed conducive and cooperative in the extension activities. Activities in the form of health counseling, discussion, question and answer, and distribution of leaflets about first aid in cases of syncope. Participants who attended seemed enthusiastic about taking part in health promotion from the beginning to the end. Questions asked by the presenter can be answered well by the participants. Based on the final evaluation, it was found that 75% of participants could mention the understanding of syncope, 85% of participants could mention the signs and symptoms of syncope, 90% of participants could practice the help done in syncope events, and 80% of participants could participate in health promotion material well.

CONCLUSION

Increasing youth knowledge in handling syncope cases in students of the Senior High School of Muhammadiyah 3 Sidoarjo, Tulangan Sub-District, Sidoarjo District was considered quite successful

because 75% of participants could mention the understanding of syncope, 85% of participants could mention the signs and symptoms of syncope, 90% of participants could practice the help done in syncope events, and 80% of participants could participate in health promotion material well.

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